

Ujrah On Extending Jéh In Islamic Jurisprudence A Comparative Study

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Abstract

Fulfilling people's needs, striving to alleviate their distress, and providing intercession are among the excellent acts of righteousness that sustain affection and friendliness and foster kind treatment. Allah's Prophets and Messengers behaved in that way. KhadĒjah (may Allah be pleased with her) said to the noble Prophet (peace be upon him): "You maintain excellent relations with your relatives, support the needy and the weak, serve your guests generously, and assist those who are afflicted by disasters." Ibn Al-Munkadir reported that he heard JĒbir (may Allah be pleased with him) saying: "The Prophet (peace be upon him) never replied in the negative to anything requested from him." Fulfilling people's needs is a form of charity offered by kind people, and ambitious personalities feel hurt when they are not invited to this cause. ×akĒm ibn ×izĒm (may Allah be pleased with him) said: "I consider the day in which I do not help anyone achieve his needs a calamity for which I expect reward from Allah." They even view those who need something from the people of JĒh as bestowers and gracious to them. Ibn ŅAbbĒs (may Allah be pleased with him) said: "There are three persons I cannot reward. First: a man making room for me in a session; even if I give him all my wealth, it will not be enough reward. Second: a man traveling for me to ask about a religious ruling; even if I spill my blood for him, it will not be enough reward. Third: a man asking me to achieve something and thinking that I am the only one who can fulfill it; only Allah Lord of the worlds can reward him." The weak are granted a righteous supplication that could better the conditions of those who fulfill the former's needs. Life is a test and full of trials. The strong, the rich, and the living may become weak, poor, and dead. The happiest of people are the ones who utilize their jĒh to benefit Muslims, and interceding with people in authority is more rewarding than voluntary acts of worship. Ibn ŅAbbĒs said: "Anyone walking to achieve his brother's right shall get a reward for every step taken." Allah promised to assist and grant success to the person who strives to fulfill people's needs. The Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "Allah will be easy with the person who is easy with insolvent people in this life and the afterlife." He also said: "Acts of goodness safeguard the doer against the evil situations, and people of goodness in this life are the people of goodness in the Hereafter." The Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "A person who alleviates the trouble of a believer in this life, Allah shall remove his trouble on the Day of Judgment." The wording of another narration reads: "Whoever wishes Allah to save him from the worries of the day of Judgement, let him give a respite to a debtor in difficult circumstances, or remit his debt." These deeds occur only by voluntarily extending jĒh to the weak, assisting people with disabilities and misery, and lending the needy. In other words, a Muslim should give money or provide a service for someone in the present time or the future without compensation and usually with the intention of righteousness and doing good. MĒlikĒ scholars said that three things should be done for the sake of Allah only: guarantee, extending jĒh, and giving loans. ŅAbdul-WĒĒid ibn ŅŌshir listed the three acts in a poetic verse, which states: "Giving loans, guarantee, and jĒh extension are forbidden to be done for the sake of other than Allah." The above introduction highlights the topic's significance because practice might be different from what has been mentioned. This situation raises the question about the legality of taking ujrah for extending jĒh. The study attempts to answer the question through three themes: defining the terms jĒh and ujrah, how permissible to take ujrah on extending jĒh is, and sample fatwas on the issue.

Introduction

Definition of JÉhExtention and Ujrah

Concept of JÉhExtention

Magnanimity is a symbol of honor and a sign of generosity that beautifies one's character. ÑAli (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "Whoever deals with people justly, speaks to them without lies, and fulfills his promises with them has perfected his magnanimity, proves to be trustworthy, deserves to be a brother, and that backbiting him is forbidden."ⁱ

Magnanimity entails relieving others through one's jÉh, which is considered the least expensive noble deed and kindest favor. It is sometimes more advantageous than giving money, serving as the last resort for people in distress and a refuge for the scared ones. JÉh commands more supporters by granting it frequently. It increases by extending it and shrinks by withholding it. There is no excuse for the person endowed with jÉh to withhold it so that he becomes worse than the stingy man who hoards his money for his calamities, personal desires, or offspring. Contrary to this situation is the one who is not benefiting others with his jÉh because he has squandered it by his greed and deprived himself of the gains that could be reaped through his position. Not only would he eventually regret the reward he missed, but also people would hate and despise him.ⁱⁱ

It was reported that the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "Human beings are all dependents of Allah, and the most beloved of them to Allah are the ones who help His dependents the most."ⁱⁱⁱ A wise man said: "Do good whenever possible, and you will be appreciated for it even later on. Bestow a favor when you are in authority, and you will be treated well when you lose it. Let the good deeds you perform in easy times be an asset for you in hard times."^{iv}

Scholars say: "The zakah of jÉh and excellent reputation is using them to alleviate people's anxieties, and thanking Allah for the blessing of jÉh requires that one invests it in dispelling people's worries and sadness through good offices." Allah the Almighty said: {Whoever intercedes for a good cause shall have a share of reward from it, and whoever intercedes for an evil cause shall have a portion of burden from it.} [Quran 4:85]^v

The word jÉh is derived from an Arabic root that means a high status and rank in the sight of people because they believe the person possesses some attributes of perfection, such as knowledge, worship, good manners, noble lineage, authority, beauty, physical strength or the like. This belief brings advantages to the person, such as praise, compliment, service, support, altruism, agreement, exaltation, and respect by initiating salam and giving him preference in all affairs.^{vi}

JÉh grows and prevails from one to another, whereas money needs extraneous efforts and hardship to multiply. When jÉh aggravates and spreads in every tongue, no wealth can stand it.^{vii} The necessity to have food, drink, and clothes requires a minimum sum of money; similarly, living with humankind requires a minimum level of jÉh.^{viii}

JÉh perishes very soon. It is like the example that Allah the Almighty mentioned, saying: {And present to them the example of the life of this world, [its being] like rain which We send down from the sky, and the vegetation of the earth mingles with it and [then] it becomes dry remnants, scattered by the winds. And Allah is ever, over all things, Perfect in Ability.} [Quran 18:45]^{ix}

Anyone whose heart is dominated by the passion for jÉh becomes obsessed with people's opinions, seeking their love earnestly and showing off. He tries by his sayings and actions to occupy a significant position in their eyes. This behavior sows the seeds of hypocrisy and corruption and ultimately leads to negligence in acts of worship, ostentation, and violation of the prohibitions to win people's hearts. That is why the Prophet (peace be upon him) resembled the passion for honor and wealth and being detrimental to one's religion as two ferocious wolves.^x KaÑb ibn MÉlik reported Allah's Messenger as saying: "Two hungry wolves free among sheep are no more damaging to the flock than a man's greed for wealth and fame is to his religion."^{xi} The Hadith means that man's greed for them is more detrimental to his religion that is as weak as sheep.^{xii}

The price for jÉh is the money that a person takes for making intercession, whether or not he stipulated, and this includes the compensation taken for transferring people from the place of fear to that of security.

Concept of Ujrah

Ujrah signifies what the leaser undertakes to pay in return for the benefit used. It refers to the compensation the lessee pays to the lessor in return for the benefit contracted. Ujrah resembles the price in a sale contract. Some scholars said that ujrah refers to the payment for the services humans offer, and kirÉ´ refers to the cost of the benefits derived from non-humans. Sometimes they are used interchangeably.

The ruling of charging ujrah on extending jÉh

Assisting people with one's jÉh reflects man's generosity and appreciation of God's blessing, and it is not praiseworthy to expect a reward for that from people. The person doing so is worthy of blame because he is

actually selling his jÉh and demanding compensation for the favors and blessings bestowed on him by Allah the Almighty. ÑAIÊ ibn ÑAbbÊsAr-RÊmÊ (may Allah have mercy on him) was reported to have said that favor should not be granted for the sake of receiving reward or compensation; instead, it should be done for free with pure intention.^{xiii}

Muslim jurists differed about the permissibility of charging ujah on helping people with jÉh into two opinions:

First: ShÉfiÑÊ and ðanbalÊ scholars said that it is permissible to take ujah on jÉh in general. From the same perspective, they allowed the person to acquire compensation from others when they borrow money through his jÉh. Al-MÊwardÊ said: “If a man requested someone to borrow for him one hundred and would reward the borrower with ten, this would be juÑÊlah (compensation).”^{xiv} Al-MÊrdÊwÊ said: “If a man specifies compensation for borrowing through one’s jÉh, this will be valid because the reward is given in return for extending jÉh only. If the compensation is made for guaranteeing him, it becomes invalid. Imam AÍmad explicitly stated these two rulings. In the second case, the rewarded intermediary serves as a guarantor, and this makes the transaction similar to a loan that is associated with a benefit.”^{xv} Imam AÍmad said: “I do not like that a person borrows on behalf of his brothers using his jÉh.” Al-QÊÊ said: “The ruling described above is applicable in case the person borrowed on his behalf is known for his default because this is considered cheating the creditor and risking his money. However, it will not be disliked if the person is known for his due settlement of debts because it is then a sort of assistance and relief.”^{xvi}

Second: MÊlikÊ scholars state three views on this issue. Some consider it forbidden, and others say it is reprehensible. The third opinion looks at the conditions of the jÉh owner: if he needs financial support or may travel and exert efforts, he is allowed to take it as ujah or fees. Otherwise, it will be forbidden.^{xvii}

Abu ÑalÊ Al-MinsÊwÊ said: “The well-studied opinion on the issue is that there is no objection to take ujah on using one’s jÉh unless the jÉh is used as a pretext to deprive others of what they deserve, particularly if they are unable to walk.”^{xviii}

Based on this, MÊlikÊ scholars held that: “A trustee should not take fees for maintaining something committed to his care because customs require preserving it for free. Preservation is a sort of jÉh that should not coommandujrah like loans and guarantees. However, the person is allowed to take ujah if he is usually hired to guard people’s belongings or if this is common in people’s customs.”^{xix}

The preponderant opinion:

I support the MÊlikÊ’s third opinion that looks at the conditions of the jÉh owner. If he requires financial support or may travel and incur hardship, he can take ujah; otherwise, it is prohibited. Helping others with one’s jÉh is not an individual obligation like fasting and prayer, and the person is not obligated to go with every person and fulfill their needs through one’s jÉh. Therefore, As-DusÊqÊ said: “The price for jÉh is forbidden because it is considered requesting money for religious obligations. A Muslim does not have to go and help all people.”^{xx}

Sample fatwas on taking ujah for extending jÉh

When Al-QÊrÊ was asked about the price for jÉh, he answered: “Our scholars differed about the price for jÉh. Some scholars say it is forbidden; others state that it is reprehensible. A third group details the issue: if the jÉh owner needs financial support or may travel and exert efforts, and he takes the usual fees, this is permissible. Otherwise, it will be forbidden. This detail is the correct opinion.”^{xxi}

Al-ÑAbdÊsÊ was asked about the person who rescues people from dangerous situations and charges fees for that, and he replied: “This work is permissible with three conditions: the person possesses a powerful jÉh that could hardly be declined; he does so only to rescue them, not because he has some private needs from this; and he agrees with them on a specified ujah or accepts whatever they will pay.”^{xxii}

Al-WansharÊsÊ was asked about a man detained wrongfully by the sultan or other oppressors and paid money for someone to help release him through his jÉh or the jÉh of someone else. Is this permissible? Is there any scholar who mentioned this ruling? Al-WansharÊsÊ said that it is acceptable. He added that a group of scholars stated this ruling, such as Al-QÊÊ ðusayn in his book At-TaÑÊqah at the beginning of Chapter: Ar-RibÊ. Al-QÊÊ also quoted this ruling from Al-QaffÊl Al-MarwazÊ, saying that it is a lawful reward like the rest of permitted compensation and cannot be classified under bribery.^{xxiii}

In FatÊwÊ An-NawawÊ, Al-QaffÊl was reported to have said: “When the person imprisoned unjustly pays money for someone to release him through the latter’s jÉh or the jÉh of someone else, this cannot be categorized as bribery; instead, it is a lawful reward like all compensations.”^{xxiv}

This opinion needs reconsideration because releasing the person imprisoned illegally is an act of forbidding evil.

Al-QaffÊl’s fatwa, however, states that if the person was detained by an oppressor and said to someone, “help release me, and I shall give you such an amount,” the helper might deserve it exactly like the

person who returns the fugitive slave. Also, it could be argued that this action is considered forbidding evil, which is a collective obligation. Releasing the detained person does absolve one from that obligation, and thus he does not deserve a reward.”^{xxv} Al-JalÉl Al-MaállÉ said: “Paying money for the person to intercede with the sultan in a lawful matter is considered permissible compensation.”^{xxvi}

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